

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

Pensarn

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The postal survey aimed to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

62 participants from Pensarn, Abergele, Towyn and Kinmel Bay (10.3% response rate)

7% aged 18-44

58% aged 45-74

32% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast =
0.71 km

Mean distance to rivers =
0.65 km

experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

have noticed
coastal change

concerned about
climate change

have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Planning restrictions

“We need to protect our environment and make the most of existing resources rather than build on our precious land ”

2 A mix of options

“As time goes on, options can then be altered to coincide with any natural changes occurring”

3 Groynes

“The groynes are already there, they just need replacing with wood again or rocks. You need to see the area and judge accordingly [...] making the best you can to defend the area with the least amount of impact on the beauty of the area being taken away”

not confident they can influence local decisions

do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among Pensarn respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>

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